

Conference Abstract

Water use and carbon accumulation in a pine forest under elevated atmospheric [CO₂]

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Abstract

The Duke Forest Free-Air CO₂ Enrichment (FACE) experiment enriched the air (eCO₂) in 30 m diameter plots to a constant +200 ppm CO₂, from 1994 to 2010. The experiment was aimed at

1. testing hypotheses generated from studies on small individuals and evaluating whether scaling was a simple matter of accounting for size differences, and
2. providing data to inform and test models used for prediction of forest behavior in the future.

The site was planted into *Pinus taeda* in 1984 but included volunteers of ~40 woody species comprising up to 50% of the leaf area index (*L*) in the poorer, more elevated plots of the relatively flat site. At the end of the study, dominant trees had reached a diameter of ~35 cm and a height of ~25 m. I will present several dominating convictions about forest response to eCO₂ and contrast these with the ultimate results from this and other FACE studies. In a nutshell, *L* reflects the intra-site variation in soil resources, and therefore the ability of the different patches of the stand to respond to eCO₂; in turn, the more a patch was able to respond, the more *L* increased. Under eCO₂, net primary production (NPP) of canopy trees increased at a given *L*, but overtime *L* increased (~18%) and NPP was mostly explained by the variation of *L* across the treatments. Despite the increase of *L*, little eCO₂ effect was observed on any component of the water cycle. As context, I will

contrast the direct effect of eCO₂ on carbon accumulation at the site with the indirect effect of climate change on storm-related carbon transfer to the detrital pool.

Presenting author

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.